

Red alert breach - case of identity theft

On some occasions, member states of the European Union claim for national security purposes, the right to infringe on individual's communications matters. Meaning, once a complete take over of the communication channels is taken over by the crime syndicate, the individual finds him or herself in a black hole of despair.

An old school modus operandi by the state actors crime syndicate

a subject of interest by the crime syndicate was an outstanding student that graduated with distinction from an US accredited academic institution, who for her own sake has the right as an alumni to continue using a university e-mail account. With such, this individual was allowed to obtain well to do jobs in important institutions like a central bank. Once at the premises, this individual witnessed a coworker using an external hard drive attached to a working computer, which was against the employer's policies. The incident was reported on different levels within the breached institution.

Aftermath

The misbehaving member state set the stage to operate on a perfect crime before the individual was granted permission to work at the central bank. Meaning, medical records were being forged to remove the rights of the individual before any security or police offices within the state. The crime of data breach happened under this subject's name and the crime syndicate went to breach communication channels of the victims. Meaning, installing keyloggers on her personal machines to obtain password, broadcasting an IP Address from the US, blocking incoming calls on operator's level, etc. As time progressed, to hide the perfect crime, the problematic member state negated the existence of the individual with abusing mental health institutes and forging medical records. Once in such institutes, communication means of the victim and documents are removed and given to whomever needs them for national security reasons.

As police channels in a member state were set up to have complete control of the victim's communication, each instance of attempting to make a crime report of digital hacking went sideways due to state corruption and agreements to bypass the communication to different individuals or it has been deleted from the victim's eyesight. The member state of the victim's citizen became a so called black hole or a prison. Meaning, the member state using a private institution to produce passports, made 2 and the real person was being discredited by the embassies and police channels to be the real person, mainly for spying purposes and money laundering.

Going into the details of a legal framework of how such a perfect crime can be possible within the 21st century is currently beyond the scope, but one thing came to life of how can such modus operandi of a state be possible to allow the crime syndicate to operate freely.

Going into the definition of threats, the penal code does not consist or define a mafia type threat to be a criminal act, therefore, the whole spectrum of harm with sedation methods and poisoning of food and drinks is not punishable by the law, therefore is legal. One other thing that is worrisome to commit such a perfect crime is the fact that no public officials laws consist of liability, if a person abuses the legal system in such a way. This is because if they define you as 'ours' no law can be applicable and one is allowed to do whatever he or she wants in the name of national security.

Breach of red alert

In the past months, a different member state initiated several investigations in different courts, mainly in two cities close to the border. On one court, the victim testified using its own means and health damages sustained by the crime syndicate, on the other court, under the same name, a different person took the stand in the court proceeding. How is this possible? Well, if a state corruption to hide traces of money laundering is so high as to the fact that police officers escort to a different member state a person that they define being somebody and such individual is also recognized by the member state embassy, then there is no doubt by the foreign authorities that the individual is truly the person who they are claiming. The situation is worrisome, because the true person knowing what the state did, is now in danger for the state crimes being committed under the victim's name and the problematic member state refuses to admit to the alleged crime.

Since the red alert has been breached, a true criminal is walking the streets and the victim needs to hide and run from the mafia because of sustained violence, sedations, spying, etc.

The detailed explanation on how it was done and what all is wrong within the European Union that such acts can be possible, will follow when time allows.